

SUSTAINABLE PACKAGING INNOVATIONS IN THE FASHION SECTOR: PROGRESS, CHALLENGES, AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

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Abstract: *The European Commission has proposed EU-wide regulations for recyclable packaging by 2030. Sustainable packaging innovations in the fashion sector have attracted public attention in recent years. However, it is uncertain how effective these companies are in reducing their use of virgin plastics, as the focus remains on improving the sustainability of garment production rather than packaging. Apparel and footwear brands are taking seven approaches to improving packaging: rethinking solutions, downsizing, eliminating plastic, reusing, recycling and composting. A study using a data-mining approach examined 400 international brands that promote sustainable packaging. The brands were categorized as progress, implementation, commitment and rethinking based on their sustainability mission statements. The results show that nearly 60% of fashion brands have made progress on sustainable packaging, with over 30% moving to improved packaging. Others have committed to future improvements. Footwear and apparel brands are adopting various sustainable packaging strategies, including The Plastic Global Commitment, Noissue Eco Packaging Alliance, One Tree Planted, The Responsible Packaging Movement and Re:Pack. This study presents the advances in sustainable packaging for apparel, footwear, accessories, etc. To manage environmental impact, sustainable packaging solutions should be evaluated on a case-by-case basis, taking into account government initiatives and regulations. Although brand manufacturers*

are striving to find better packaging solutions, innovation in this area remains restrained.

Keywords: Sustainable packaging, fashion sector, plastic reduction, packaging innovations, apparel and footwear brands.

1 INTRODUCTION

The fashion industry has long been synonymous with creativity, style and self-expression. However, its rapid growth and global expansion have also led to significant environmental challenges, particularly in terms of packaging waste. As the fashion sector has taken center stage in addressing sustainability issues, there has been an increased focus on adopting environmentally friendly practices, with particular attention paid to sustainable packaging solutions. This study looks at the evolving landscape of sustainable packaging initiatives in the fashion industry. With the goal of reducing the harmful effects of packaging on the environment, numerous fashion brands have committed to redesigning their packaging to be reusable, recyclable or compostable. The urgency to curb plastic pollution has been reinforced by the European Commission's proposed EU-wide regulations that require all packaging to be recyclable by 2030 (European packaging waste, 2023). Despite the increased attention given to sustainable packaging innovations in recent years, the transition has not been without challenges. Fashion brands have historically prioritized improving the sustainability of their apparel production, often relegating the importance of sustainable packaging to the background (Boz et al., 2020, Ahmed et. al., 2021). This represents a knowledge gap when it comes to how effectively companies in the fashion sector are addressing the critical issue of reducing the consumption of virgin plastics (García-Arca et al., 2017; Escursell et al., 2021). This study takes a comprehensive approach by examining the multiple strategies used by apparel and footwear brands to improve the sustainability of their packaging. In addition, this research provides a detailed analysis of the different approaches used by fashion brands to improve their packaging. The "7R" framework, which includes rethinking solutions, reducing, reusing, repurpose, refuse, recycling and rot packaging, serves as the guiding principle for our research (Jestratišević et. al, 2022).

The 7 R's of Sustainability: Eco-Friendly packaging solutions are (Jestratišević et al., 2022):

1. Rethink: Businesses should reconsider traditional plastic and paper wrapping methods, exploring eco-friendly alternatives like bioplastics derived from

renewable sources, reducing the environmental impact of packaging materials.

2. Refuse: Advocate avoiding single-use plastics such as bags, cutlery, and straws, while rejecting overpackaging practices to reduce plastic waste and its adverse effects.
3. Reduce: Emphasize minimizing the need for certain products or packaging by opting for reusable containers and environmentally friendly materials that cannot be easily recycled.
4. Repurpose: Encourage businesses to transform discarded items into useful products, prolonging the life cycle of materials and reducing overall waste.
5. Reuse: Emphasize the benefits of reusing materials like cardboard, PET, HDPE, or investing in durable containers like glass or stainless steel to promote sustainable packaging practices.
6. Recycle: Prioritize recycling to keep materials at their highest value for as long as possible, considering factors like shape, size, and composition to optimize the recycling process.
7. Rot: Composting organic matter offers a solution for packaging contaminated with food scraps, contributing to nutrient-rich soil production and reducing landfill waste.

By providing up-to-date insights into the practical progress of sustainable packaging in the fashion industry, this study aims to stimulate further discussion and action. We emphasize the need for case-by-case consideration of sustainable packaging solutions, considering the complex interplay between environmental impacts and government regulations. Ultimately, this research aims to contribute to ongoing efforts to make the fashion industry more sustainable by addressing the critical role of packaging practices in sustaining our planet for future generations.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

A systematic review methodology was employed, using data-mining to collect sustainable packaging information from eligible brands (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2020). Only primary sources from brands' official websites and sustainability reports were reviewed, excluding secondary sources like social media and press articles without a link from the brand's website from November 2020 to January 2021. The final sample comprised 400 brands from various sectors and continents. Thematic content clustering facilitated iterative data analysis through five research stages.

3 RESULTS

European brands were found to lead innovation in sustainable packaging innovation with 55% of the sample (n=218). North America followed with 28% (n=113) of fashion brands offering sustainable packaging solutions, while South American, Australian, Asian and African regions accounted for 2-11% of the total sample (Figure 1a). In addition, the research showed that fashion brands in certain regions tend to comply with national and local regulations that influence their packaging choices. European brands were observed to avoid using single-use plastic bags, while brands in Australia often offer packaging that is 100% recyclable, compostable or biodegradable. In addition, sustainably oriented retailers in Africa and Asia often sourced packaging materials locally from artisanal communities.

Figure 1. a) Distribution of analyzed brands across five continents; b) Subcategories per product category and number of brands.

Further analysis focused on the relationship between packaging improvements and specific product categories. Results revealed that clothing brands (45.5%) were the most committed to improving their primary packaging, which directly protects the product. Footwear (5%), accessories (6.25%), underwear, and socks (3.75%) brands followed with improvements in their primary packaging. Secondary packaging improvements were seen in footwear, accessories, and jewelry categories, while many brands did not specify the types of packaging they improved. Sustainability-related packaging certifications were explored, indicating that only a limited number of brands used such certifications. Among 400 analyzed brands, 55 had Forest management certification (FSC certificate), 24 promoted the Global Organic Textile Standard (GOTS), and 17 advertised having the Global Recycle Standard (GRS) for their packaging products. Most

brands (284) had no packaging certificates, raising questions about the sincerity of their sustainable packaging commitments.

Figure 2. The shift from traditional to improved packaging solution.

Our findings illuminate the progress nearly 60% of fashion brands have made in adopting sustainable packaging practices, with over 30% having already initiated the shift from traditional to improved packaging solutions (Figure 2). The remaining brands have committed to rethinking or improving their packaging strategies in the near future.

We also examined the specific sustainable packaging strategies of leading apparel and footwear brands, highlighting prominent initiatives such as The Plastic Global Commitment, Noissue Eco Packaging Alliance, One Tree Planted, The Responsible Packaging Movement and Re:Pack.

The research demonstrated varied trends in sustainable packaging practices among fashion brands across different geographic regions. European brands led in sustainable packaging innovations, while the adoption of sustainable packaging certificates and partnerships remained relatively low.

3. 1 Opportunities

European fashion brands have demonstrated leadership in sustainable packaging innovation, presenting an opportunity for other regions and brands to follow suit (Islam et al., 2021). By adopting eco-friendly practices, fashion brands can position themselves as industry leaders in sustainability and attract environmentally conscious consumers. The study identified stronger preferences for sustainable product attributes among specific categories of consumers.

Understanding and catering to these preferences can open up new market segments and increase brand loyalty among environmentally conscious customers. Fashion brands in Africa and Asia have successfully sourced packaging materials from local artisanal communities. This presents an opportunity for other brands to support local economies and showcase their commitment to sustainable sourcing practices.

3. 2 Progress and challenges

The prevalence of sustainable packaging certifications is still relatively low among the fashion brands studied. Overcoming the challenges associated with obtaining and promoting such certifications could be a hurdle for many brands seeking to establish themselves in the sustainability credentials. On the other hand, some fashion brands didn't specify the types of packaging they improved. This lack of transparency may create doubts among consumers regarding the authenticity of a brand's sustainability claims, highlighting the importance of clear and open communication (Chirilli et. al., 2022). While there are partnerships focusing on sustainable packaging, a significant number of brands still lack such collaborations. Establishing strategic partnerships can be challenging due to resource allocation and alignment of long-term goals.

3. 3 Future perspective

As consumers become more environmentally conscious and demand eco-friendly practices, fashion brands are likely to increasingly adopt sustainable packaging solutions. This shift could drive industry-wide improvements and encourage the development of new eco-friendly packaging materials and technologies. The study revealed that clothing brands were most committed to improving their primary packaging. In the future, there may be a greater emphasis on developing innovative packaging solutions for other product categories, such as footwear, accessories, and jewelry, to further reduce environmental impact. The growing awareness and demand for sustainable practices may lead to an increased focus on obtaining and promoting credible packaging certifications. Brands that prioritize obtaining recognized certifications could gain a competitive advantage in the market. The fashion industry may witness more widespread collaboration and partnerships among brands and packaging providers to develop comprehensive, sustainable packaging solutions. These efforts could accelerate the transition to environmentally friendly packaging practices.

4 CONCLUSION

The findings from the study present both opportunities and challenges for the fashion industry's adoption of sustainable packaging. Embracing innovative practices, promoting transparency, and collaborating with stakeholders will be crucial for shaping a more sustainable future for fashion packaging. As consumer awareness continues to grow, sustainable packaging will likely become an essential aspect of a brand's overall sustainability strategy.

The main considerations and challenges that addressing sustainable packaging in this field are:

- Certification: Ensure compostable packaging is certified as home or industrially compostable.
- Collection and recycling infrastructure: Regional variations in recycling facilities may impact material choices.
- Contamination: Prevent contamination during recycling to maintain recyclability.
- Cost and viability: Initial costs and logistical challenges may be offset by long-term benefits and improved consumer perception.

The progress made in sustainable packaging in the fashion industry is encouraging, but there is still much room for improvement. With growing consumer awareness and demands for environmentally friendly practices, fashion brands are expected to continue their journey towards more sustainable packaging solutions, contributing to a greener and more responsible fashion industry.

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